

Fine-Tuning Open-Source LLMs on Multi-Turn CBT Conversations

Rishabh Balse, Sam Nallaperuma-Herzberg, and Pietro Liò

Department of Computer Science and Technology, University of Cambridge, CB3 0FD, UK {rmb220, snn26, p1219}@cam.ac.uk

Abstract. Large language models (LLMs) have shown considerable promise in supporting mental health interventions. However, concerns around data privacy, content moderation, and transparency limit the practical use of proprietary models in sensitive settings. In this study, we propose two therapy generation models that can generate cognitive behavioural therapy (CBT)-style therapeutic dialogues. Moreover, we investigate whether a fine-tuned open-source model can match the performance of a closed-source alternative in generating CBT. Using a dataset of 7,000 multi-turn conversations, we fine-tuned Llama 3.1 8B using Quantized Low-Rank Adaptation (QLoRA) and compared it against a fine-tuned version of GPT-4o-mini. Preliminary results show that Llama3 slightly outperforms GPT-4o-mini on metrics favoring semantic coverage and recall, while GPT-4o-mini demonstrates stronger precision and fluency. Despite statistically significant differences, most effect sizes were small, suggesting that both models are comparably effective depending on task requirements.

Keywords: Large language models · Mental health · cognitive behavioural therapy · fine-tuning.

1 Introduction

The emergence of large language models (LLMs) has opened up new opportunities for providing scalable, low-cost support in mental health contexts, ranging from psychoeducation to therapeutic conversations and emotional support [6, 4]. Models like GPT-4 and Gemini have shown clear potential in supporting cognitive tasks such as identifying unhelpful thoughts and offering alternative reframings [3]. In some cases, they have even outperformed trained medical professionals, for example, in diagnosing conditions like obsessive compulsive disorder (OCD) from clinical vignettes [5]. Despite these promising developments, the use of closed-source LLMs in mental health raises a number of ethical, cultural, and practical concerns [2, 8]

One of the most pressing issues is the handling of sensitive personal data that naturally arises in therapeutic conversations. Users and practitioners often have limited visibility into how closed models process or store this information, raising concerns about data privacy, security, and regulatory compliance. Prior work has

shown that LLMs can inadvertently memorise and reproduce sensitive training data, adding further risk to their deployment in clinical or research settings [9].

Discussions in mental health contexts frequently involve topics that are distressing or explicit. To mitigate the generation of harmful content, companies like OpenAI have implemented stringent content moderation policies. These policies include safeguards against producing content related to self-harm, trauma, or other sensitive subjects ¹. While these measures aim to protect users, they can inadvertently hinder meaningful conversations about critical mental health issues.

In light of these challenges, researchers have increasingly turned to fine-tuning open-source LLMs for specific mental health tasks, with encouraging results. Models such as Mental-Alpaca and Mental-FLAN-T5 have been shown to outperform larger general-purpose models like GPT-3.5 on classification tasks in mental health [11]. Similarly, domain-specific models like CBT-LLM [10] produce more structured and contextually relevant responses when interacting in CBT-style conversations, compared to untuned baselines.

In this paper, we investigate whether a fine-tuned open-source LLM, trained on multi-turn CBT-style dialogues, can approximate the performance of a closed-source counterpart. Specifically, we (1) propose two therapy generation models capable of producing CBT-style conversations, and (2) evaluate their performance using standard objective metrics for text generation.

Our results show that both models have complementary strengths, with comparable overall performance depending on evaluation focus.

2 Proposed Approach

The base dataset for the exercise was drawn from Lee et al. [7], which provides structured multi-turn conversations categorised according to specific CBT techniques.

2.1 Dataset Preparation

Following the guideline from Xu et al. [11], which suggests a saturation point of approximately 6,500 examples for fine-tuning, we selected 1,000 examples each from the top seven CBT techniques featured in the Lee et al. dataset. These techniques were:

- Alternative Perspective
- Reality Testing
- Behavior Experiment
- Decatastrophizing
- Efficiency Evaluation
- Changing Rules to Wishes
- Problem-Solving Skills Training

¹ <https://model-spec.openai.com/2025-02-12.html>

Each technique’s dataset was split into training and testing subsets with an approximate 93:7 ratio, yielding a total of 6,503 training examples and 497 testing examples.

2.2 Model Fine-Tuning

Two models were fine-tuned on the prepared dataset:

- **Llama 3.1 8B**: Fine-tuned using QLoRA [1] via the PyTorch and Unsloth libraries. Training was conducted on a single NVIDIA A100-SXM4 GPU with 80 GB VRAM.
- **GPT-4o-mini**: Fine-tuned using OpenAI’s proprietary fine-tuning platform.

Both models were trained using the same hyperparameters:

- **Batch size**: 32
- **Epochs**: 4
- **Learning rate**: 1×10^{-5}

2.3 Evaluation Metrics

After fine-tuning, both models were evaluated using standard text generation metrics: ROUGE (1, 2, L), BLEU (1, 2), and BERTScore (Precision, Recall, F1). Each multi-turn dialogue was evaluated on a turn-by-turn basis, and the scores were averaged across all turns to produce final metric values.

3 Results

Table 1. Model Performance Comparison (Higher values are better)

Metric	Llama3 Mean	GPT-4o Mean	Difference	Cohen’s d	Interpretation
ROUGE-1	0.3363	0.3225	+0.0138	0.103	Small Llama3 advantage
ROUGE-2	0.1288	0.1139	+0.0149	0.121	Small Llama3 advantage
ROUGE-L	0.2607	0.2563	+0.0044	0.034	Negligible difference
BLEU-1	0.2990	0.3466	-0.0476	-0.356	Moderate GPT-4o advantage
BLEU-2	0.1657	0.1572	+0.0085	0.063	Negligible difference
BERT-P	0.8893	0.8982	-0.0089	-0.317	Moderate GPT-4o advantage
BERT-R	0.9031	0.8986	+0.0045	0.219	Small Llama3 advantage
BERT-F1	0.8961	0.8984	-0.0023	-0.101	Negligible difference

The evaluations in 1 reveal differences between Llama3 and GPT-4o-mini across metrics (all comparisons statistically significant at $p < 0.0001$). Both

Llama3 and GPT-4o-mini showed clear strengths and weaknesses when evaluated on multi-turn CBT dialogues. Llama3 performed slightly better on ROUGE metrics and BERT Recall, indicating it closely followed the reference conversation scripts and captured a broader range of meaningful content. On the other hand, GPT-4o-mini showed stronger performance in metrics focused on precise wording and meaning, specifically BLEU-1 and BERT Precision, suggesting more nuanced and contextually precise responses.

4 Discussion

This study proposed two language models, a fine-tuned open-source model, Llama3 and a closed-source model, GPT-4o-mini both capable of generating digital therapy for mental health. Moreover, this study examined the comparative performance of the proposed models, in multi-turn CBT-style dialogues. While both models demonstrated statistically significant differences across standard text similarity metrics, most effect sizes were small, indicating that their overall performance was broadly comparable.

Llama3 showed modest advantages in semantic coverage and alignment with reference scripts, whereas GPT-4o-mini tended to generate more concise and context-sensitive responses. These results suggest that the choice between models may depend more on task-specific priorities, such as ticking closely to the conversation format versus using more precise language, rather than on a clear overall winner.

However, surface level similarity does not necessarily reflect qualities such as empathy, appropriateness, or therapeutic usefulness. As such, a key direction for future work could be to conduct detailed human evaluations, involving both mental health practitioners and individuals with lived experience, to assess how these models are perceived.

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